

Sprouts from the overwintered stubble of Dongxiang wild rice.

Hunan, and Jiangxi provinces and planted in ricefields in Wuhan District. Normal management practices were followed. Plants were left in the field to overwinter naturally. Many seedlings were growing in the stubble in the spring of 1994. Seedlings were pulled up to ascertain from where they came. Most had germinated from seeds shed during the previous year, but some had sprouted from underground stems.

Dongxiang wild rice was retested in 1994. This time, the panicles were bagged after heading and the aboveground plant parts were cut off to prevent seed-germinated seedlings. Only stubble remained over winter. In the spring of 1995, when the seedlings were about 15 cm, stubble was removed to inspect growth (see figure). The underground stems were yellowish green and viable, and the roots were white and able to support new plant growth. The underground stem had three nodes, with 1-3 seedlings or buds regenerating from each (see figure).

Sprouted seedlings were transplanted into pots and into the field. Those germinated from seeds served as a control. The plants in pots were subjected to a 10-h short-day treatment. Heading occurred in late July. The average seed-setting rate was 54%, which was the same as for the control. The spikelets turned black at maturity and were prone to shattering. The plants in the field grew vigorously and developed more

than 30 tillers per hill. Heading occurred in late September.

Wuhan is 2.3 ° higher in latitude than is Dongxiang County. The extreme minimum winter temperatures were -8.0 °C in 1993 and -3.5 °C in 1994. The underground stems and roots of Dongxiang wild rice have strong cold tolerance, enabling the plants to survive the winter and to grow again in early spring.

Dongxiang wild rice is an ideal source of cold tolerance. It could potentially be used to develop a new type of rice that can overwinter in rice-growing areas with climates similar to that of central China. ■

Genetic basis of variation in weedy rice collected from Republic of Korea

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Variations in morphophysiological characters—such as grain shape (length/width ratio), glume hair length, 100-grain weight, resistance to KClO₃ phenol reaction, seed dormancy, and seed shattering—and allelic variation at 14 isozyme loci were tested for 141 strains of weedy rice selected randomly from more

than 1,000 strains collected from farmers' fields in the Republic of Korea. We investigated variations in 37 restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) and 13 randomly amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) markers from 24 strains in addition to seed fertility of F₁s between weedy and cultivated rices.

Based on grain shape, Korean weedy rices were classified into long- and short-grained types. The long-grained type came only from the southern regions of the peninsula, while the short-grained type was distributed throughout the peninsula. The F₁s of long-grained weedy rice and indica testers had 48% seed fertility and those with japonica testers, 27%. Those of short-grained weedy rice and indica testers had 37% seed fertility and those with japonica testers, 69%.

By principal component analysis based on morphophysiological characters and isozyme variations, the weedy rice strains were divided into two distinct groups (see figure). All of the long-grained strains were grouped into the same cluster as indica cultivars IR36 and Peh-kuh; all of the short-grained types were clustered with japonica cultivars Taichung 65 and Nakdongbyeon. In RFLP analysis, a high level of polymorphism was found between long-grained and short-grained type, while lower polymorphism was found within each grain type. Variations in the short-grained type were narrow but those in the long-grained type were broad. The long- and short-grained types were also distinctly classified by RAPD markers.

Scatter diagram of 141 strains of Korean weedy rices by the first vectors of principal component analysis based on morphophysiological (I_m) and isozyme (I_i) variations.

Based on morphophysiological characters, F_1 fertility, variations in isozymes, and RFLP and RAPD markers, the Korean short-grained weedy rices are a relatively uniform group similar to typical japonicas, while the long-grained weedy rices are diverse and more similar to indica cultivars than to japonica cultivars. ■

Allozyme variability and inter- and intrapopulation gene diversity of *Oryza glumaepatula* in the Amazon Basin

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Oryza glumaepatula is a diploid wild rice species with the AA genome. It is found in tropical Central and South America. One of its unique ecotypes grows in the Amazon Basin, where water levels annually oscillate by as much as 10 m. The culms of these plants easily break at a specific growth stage. With no roots to anchor them to the ground, the plants float on the water and move downstream with the river current and wind.

To analyze the gene flow system and genetic diversity of populations of Amazonian *O. glumaepatula*, we examined allozyme variability of 30 loci of 16 enzymes from 34 natural populations distributed in five regions. Several parameters, including fixation index and Nei's gene

Summary of allozyme variation in *O. glumaepatula* for 30 loci of 16 enzymes within several regions: proportion of polymorphic loci (P), mean number of alleles per locus (A), observed heterozygosity (H_{obs}), and Nei's gene diversity parameters.^a

	Populations (no.)	P	A	H_{obs}	H_T^a	H_S^a	D_{ST}^a	G_{ST}^a
Rio Negro 1	3	0.20	1.27	0.002	0.059	0.040	0.018	0.310
Rio Negro 2	6	0.27	1.27	0.001	0.054	0.026	0.028	0.521
Rio Solimões 1	11	0.67	1.77	0.006	0.119	0.071	0.048	0.403
Rio Solimões 2	8	0.53	1.63	0.002	0.091	0.052	0.039	0.430
Rio Solimões 3	6	0.23	1.23	0.002	0.009	0.008	0.001	0.109
Total	34	0.73	1.93	0.003	0.109	0.043	0.067	0.610
Interregion	5	-	-	-	0.118	0.068	0.050	0.421

^a H_T = expected heterozygosity, H_S = intrapopulation gene diversity, D_{ST} = interpopulation gene diversity, G_{ST} = coefficient of genetic differentiation.

diversity, were used to assess allozyme variability of each region.

Allozymes were not so variable, although populations examined were collected from nearly 20,000 km². Overall genetic diversity had low values compared with those of the Asian wild rice, *O. rufipogon*. But population genotypes tend to be differentiated among regions isolated geographically.

In Rio Solimões, the main river of the Amazon, diversity, measured as the proportion of polymorphic loci (P), average number of alleles per locus (A), and total heterozygosity (H_T = expected heterozygosity), was found to increase when going from the upper to the lower basin (see table). Gene flow most probably proceeds in a one-way direction from the upper to the lower Amazon basin.

In Rio Negro, one of the Amazon's largest tributaries, diversity was not different between the upper and lower basins. The Rio Negro's water has poor

nutrition and low pH compared with that of other rivers, making it unfavorable for plant growth. *O. glumaepatula* colonization in the Rio Negro is limited.

Observed heterozygosities (H_{obs}) were much lower than expected, and the fixation index averaged over P was nearly equal to 1 ($F_{IS} = 0.954$). This indicates that Amazonian *O. glumaepatula* has developed self-pollination systems, enabling it to produce seed under unstable conditions. *O. glumaepatula* did not show clear population differentiation when compared with predominantly selfing annual populations of *O. rufipogon* that show higher interpopulation gene diversity (D_{ST}) rather than intrapopulation gene diversity (H_S) (see table). The degree of gene flow among populations is probably much higher in *O. glumaepatula* than in *O. rufipogon*.

The ability to float on water and self-pollination are important factors responsible for the genetic diversity observed in Amazonian *O. glumaepatula*. ■

Germplasm use in Ecuador and Bolivia

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IRRI and CIAT coordinate the International Network for Genetic Evaluation of Rice for Latin America and the Caribbean (INGER-LAC). Since its inception in 1976, countries in the region have actively used the network to exchange germplasm and information.

INGER-LAC has distributed 5,458 advanced lines to national partners through

2,272 nursery sets of 14 types from 1979 to 1993. To better understand and document the value of this service, we compared the use of introduced germplasm by national programs in Ecuador and Bolivia. We considered the number of nurseries (lines) introduced, number of varieties released from them, time taken to release a variety from an introduced line, and efforts needed to release a variety.

Information was obtained from the INGER-LAC data base. From the nurseries requested and dispatched to the two countries, we determined the number of lines introduced yearly. Ecuador released

three varieties and Bolivia, six (Tables 1 and 2).

The period covered was the time between the release of the first variety and the release of the most recent variety in each country. Having identified the first variety released, we then determined the year in which the line was introduced. The first variety was released in Ecuador in 1986, based on a line from a 1982 nursery, and in Bolivia, in 1987 from a line provided in a 1979 nursery.

Ecuador introduced 3,201 lines from 64 nurseries and released three varieties from 1982 to 1994. The national program evaluated an average of 915 lines to release a